

Marsupials

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Bettongia lesueur – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Bettongia lesueur – Ventral: None (some tannin fluorescence visible on exposed skin along stitching)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Dasyurus geoffroyi – Dorsal: White

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Dasyurus geoffroyi – Ventral: White

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Didelphis virginiana (right); *Philander opossum* (left) – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Didelphis virginiana (right) & *Philander opossum* (left) – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Didelphis virginiana – Dorsal: Pink/Blue (Pink along dorsal stripe, blue along white stripes)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Didelphis virginiana – Ventral: Inconclusive (Some pink)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Marmosa sp. – Dorsal: Pink; *Micoureus demerarae* – Dorsal: Pink

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Marmosa mexicana

Marmosa murina

Micoureus demerarae

Desaturated pigmentation may partially indicate an older adult or older preserved specimen (check dates)

Marmosa sp. – Ventral: Pink; *Micoureus demerarae* – Ventral: Pink

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Petaurus australis – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Petaurus australis – Ventral: None (Possible UVF in nails)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Petaurus breviceps – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Petaurus breviceps – Ventral: Inconclusive (potentially pink and blue on abdomen)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Trichosurus vulpecula – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Trichosurus vulpecula – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Trichosaurus vulpecula – Dorsal: Inconclusive (potentially pink along shoulders and upper back)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Trichosaurus vulpecula – Ventral: Inconclusive (potentially weak pink around base of upper limbs)

Primates and Relatives

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Aotus trivirgatus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Aotus trivirgatus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Arctocebus calabarensis – Dorsal: White (Note abdomen is bright with darkened forelimbs in edit)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Arctocebus calabarensis – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Avahi laniger – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Avahi laniger – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Callithrix jacchus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Callithrix jacchus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Callithrix pencillata – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Callithrix pencillata – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Euoticus elegantulus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Euoticus elegantulus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Galago senegalensis – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Galago senegalensis – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Galeopterus variegatus – Dorsal: Inconclusive

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Galeopterus variegatus – Ventral: None (Very bright cyan is exposed skin, colour consistent with contamination)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Lagothrix lagothricha – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Lagothrix lagotricha – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Leontocebus fuscicollis – None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Microcebus murinus – Dorsal: Pink (Cap and dorsal stripe)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Microcebus murinus – Pink (Cap and facial markings)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Otolemur garnettii – Dorsal: Inconclusive (potentially weak pink on forearms)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Otolemur garnettii – Ventral: Inconclusive (potentially pink weak under chin, on chest and forelimbs)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Plecturocebus moloch – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Plecturocebus moloch – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Saimiri sciureus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Saimiri sciureus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Tarsius tarsier – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Tarsius tarsier – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Tupaia belangeri – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Tupaia belangeri – Ventral: None

Rodents

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Anolamurus derbianus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Anolamurus derbianus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Anolamurus sp. – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Anolamurus sp. – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Callosciurus caniceps – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Callosciurus caniceps – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Callospermophilus lateralis – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Callospermophilus lateralis – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Cynomys gunnisoni – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Cynomys gunnisoni – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Cynomys ludvicianus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Cynomys ludvicianus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Cynomys ludovicianus – Dorsal: Inconclusive (Fur is bright in edit, but patterning is consistent with white conditions)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Cynomys ludovicianus – Ventral: Inconclusive (see Dorsal notes)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Glaucomys sabrinus – Dorsal: BC: None; MB, NWT, YK: Pink (Very weak in MB and NWT)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Glaucomys sabrinus – Ventral: BC: None/Weak; MB, NWT, YK: Pink

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Glaucomys volans – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Glaucomys volans – Ventral: 1958, 1977, 1986: None; 1975: Pink

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Ictidomys tridecemlineatus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Ictidomys tridecemlineatus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Marmota flaviventris – Dorsal: Inconclusive (Guard hairs potentially blue/white)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Marmota flaviventris – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Marmota vancouverensis – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Marmota vancouverensis – Ventral: Inconclusive (white patches potentially white/blue)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Mus musculus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Mus musculus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Myomorpha - Dorsal: *M. musculus*, *O. torridus*, *P. californicus* – None; *R. mexicanus* – Pink

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Myomorpha – Dorsal: *M. musculus* – None; *O. torridus*, *P. californicus*, *R. mexicanus* – White

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Onychomys leucogaster – Dorsal: 1920, 1921, 1960 – None; 1963, 1983 – Pink

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Onychomys leucogaster – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Onychomys torridus – Dorsal: Pink/Blue

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Onychomys torridus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Otospermophilus beecheyi – Dorsal: White

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Otospermophilus beecheyi – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Otospermophilus variegatus – Dorsal: White

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Otospermophilus variegatus – Ventral: White

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Peromyscus californicus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Peromyscus californicus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

AZ, 1971 AZ, 1983 AZ, 1981

Peromyscus eremicus – Dorsal: 1971 – None; 1981, 1983 – Pink

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Peromyscus eremicus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Peromyscus leucopus & *P. maniculatus* – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

P. maniculatus

Peromyscus leucopus & *P. maniculatus* – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Peromyscus polionotus – Dorsal: Left – None; Right – Inconclusive

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Peromyscus polionotus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Petaurista alborufus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Petaurista alborufus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Petaurista leucogenys – Dorsal: Inconclusive (Potentially blue guard hairs)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

- Edited

Petaurista leucogenys – Ventral: Inconclusive (Some pink on white abdominal hairs)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Petaurista petaurista – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Petaurista petaurista – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Sciurus aberti – Dorsal: Inconclusive (potential blue/white guard hairs)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Sciurus aberti – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Sciurus sp. (Unknown) – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Sciurus sp. (Unknown) – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Sicista subtilis – Dorsal/Right: Blue/Green

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Sicista subtilis – Ventral/Left: Blue/Green

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Spermophilus citellus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Spermophilus citellus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Spermophilus suslicus – Dorsal: White

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Spermophilus suslicus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Tamias spp. – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Tamias spp. – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Tamias amoenus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Tamias amoenus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Tamias merriami – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Tamias merriami – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Tamias sibiricus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Tamias sibiricus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Tamiasciurus douglasii –Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Tamiasciurus douglasii – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Urocitellus armatus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Urocitellus armatus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Urocitellus beldingi – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Urocitellus beldingi – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Urocitellus columbianus – Dorsal: Inconclusive (Spots potentially blue/white)

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Urocitellus columbianus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Urocitellus richardsonii – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Urocitellus richardsonii – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Urocitellus undulatus – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Urocitellus undulatus – Ventral: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Xerospermophilus spilosoma – Dorsal: None

White Light

UV

UV – Yellow Filter

UV - Edited

Xerospermophilus spilosoma – Ventral: None